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TRANSIENT PROCESSES IN RELIEF SECTIONS OF PIPELINES FOR TRANSPORTING INCOMPRESSIBLE FLUIDS, FORMED BY CHANGES IN SPEED AT THE ENDS OF THE RELIEF SECTION

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Abstract. Within the framework of the non-conservative form of quasi-one-dimensional linearized equations N.E. Zhukovsky formulated the problem of a transient process on an elementary relief section of a pipeline when the boundary velocities of an incompressible fluid change over time. The incomplete telegraph equation, compiled for the averaged flow velocity, is solved by the method of separation of variables. The pressure value was obtained by integrating the original equations using the resulting velocity solution. Numerical results concerning the case of constant values of functions in initial and boundary conditions are presented. Variants of constant, increasing and decreasing average pressure values over the area are identified. Features of the behavior of shock waves with and without taking into account the friction force are revealed.

Keywords: pipeline, low-compressibility fluid, resistance force, gravity, quasionedimensional model, Fure method, computational experiment.

1 INTRODUCTION

In engineering practice, hydraulic calculations of pipelines and their networks are carried out according to indicators of stationary flow far from disturbed zones [1]. In this regard, bottlenecks in the pipeline network appear when considering non-stationary problems. A typical example of non-stationary problems is the problem of transient processes. The transition from one regime state to another is usually accompanied by phenomena that require simultaneous consideration of two speed scales: hydrodynamic speed and the speed of propagation of small disturbances in the pipe-transported medium system.

The formation and propagation of disturbance waves in pipelines are studied within the framework of quasi-one-dimensional equations by N.E. Zhukovsky [2,3]. He was the first to construct a system of quasi-one-dimensional equations that simultaneously take into account the hydrodynamic velocity of the fluid and the speed of propagation of small disturbances in the

medium-pipeline system, and carried out theoretical and experimental studies on the propagation of compaction and vacuum waves in pipelines.

The development and widespread practical application of pipeline networks are directly related to theoretical research. Various linear and nonlinear, complete and simplified mathematical models of pipeline transportation of low- and super-compressible media [4] and hydrodynamic mixtures within the framework of Newtonian and non-Newtonian media [5] have been developed. Analytical [6,7], numerical [8,9] and approximate methods for solving problems for the network and its individual sections have been developed, with or without taking into account individual power and energy factors.

Problems on the propagation of compaction and rarefaction waves are of particular interest for science and practice. Multiple repetitions of such waves lead to loss of pipeline integrity. Let us give two examples that demonstrate the destructive consequences of repetitions of alternating waves of compaction and rarefaction.

Pipeline power plants (pumps, compressors) operate within a certain range of input pressure and flow rate. Their smaller values lead to the phenomenon of surge : a strong oscillatory process is formed in the transported medium. These vibrations are then transmitted to the pipeline body and the supercharger. The coincidence of the natural frequencies of the housing and the transported medium leads to a resonant event, which ultimately damages the supercharger and pipeline.

Starting and stopping units of pumping stations is accompanied by the formation of waves of pressure disturbances in large, destructive intervals [10].

In general, studying the features of the formation and propagation of shock waves is of great interest. The difficulty of studying shock waves is associated with jumps in indicators. This applies to both theoretical research and bench research. In the first case, this is due to the use of the Heaviside function [11] or the introduction of traveling waves and the development of adequate numerical methods [12,13]. In the second case, this is due to the development and use of less inertial measurement systems with the support of modern computer technologies [14,15].

Based on these features of the shock wave and the research needs of engineering practice, below we consider an elementary relief section of the pipeline, at both ends of which the laws of velocity change over time are specified. The initial distributions of velocity and its time derivative are known. It is required to solve the problem by the Fourier method within the framework of the quasi-one-dimensional model N.E. Zhukovsky.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

A general solution to the problem is proposed, taking into account the force factors of friction, gravity and the local component of the inertia force at variable input and output speeds. Numerical results were obtained for constant values of the functions appearing in the initial and boundary conditions. Unlike known solutions, the topography of the pipeline route is taken into account here.

Let's imagine a mathematical model of the problem.

The dynamic state of the liquid in an elementary section of the pipeline at $\rho \approx const$ is described by the equations [2,16]:

$$\begin{cases} -\frac{\partial P}{\partial x} = \rho \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + 2aw \right), \\ -\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = \rho c^2 \frac{\partial w}{\partial x}. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Here $P(x,t) = p(x,t) + \rho gy(x)$ – total hydrostatic pressure, representing a measure of the energy loss of the fluid; $p(x,t)$, $w(x,t)$ – cross-sectional average x values of pressure and flow velocity at the moment of time t ; $y(x)$ – leveling height of the pipeline axis; $a = \frac{\lambda w_*}{4D}$; w_* – characteristic rate of the process – averaging parameter; λ – coefficient of friction resistance; $c = \left(\frac{\rho_0}{k} + \frac{D\rho_0}{E\delta} \right)^{-1/2}$ – speed of propagation of small pressure disturbances in the pipe-liquid system; ρ_0 , D – liquid density and pipeline diameter in an undisturbed state; k , E – elastic moduli of the transported liquid and pipe; δ – pipe thickness [16].

Elimination of total pressure $P(x,t)$ at a constant cross-sectional area of the pipe $f = \pi D^2 / 4$ allows you to construct a separate equation for speed:

$$\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} + 2a \frac{\partial w}{\partial t} = c^2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}.$$

This is an incomplete telegraph equation [17,16].

The following initial conditions are considered:

$$w(x,0) = w^{(0)}(x), \quad \frac{\partial w(x,0)}{\partial t} = w^{(t)}(x).$$

Boundary conditions are specified in the form

$$w(0,t) = \bar{w}(t), \quad w(l,t) = \tilde{w}(t).$$

According to these data and the first equation of the original system, the initial condition for the total pressure is

$$P(x,0) = p_{00} - \rho \int_0^x \left[w^{(t)}(\eta) + 2aw^{(0)}(\eta) \right] d\eta,$$

where p_{00} – is the initial pressure in the inlet section.

If the second condition is given in the form $P(x,0) = p_0(x)$, then, using the first equation of the original system, it can be transformed, i.e. two types of the second condition lead to the same result.

Let us reduce the boundary conditions to a homogeneous form. For this purpose, a new required function is introduced $u(x,t)$ according to the dependence

$$w(x,t) = C_0(t) + xC_1(t) + u(x,t).$$

Function values defined

$$C_0(t) = \bar{w}(t), \quad C_1(t) = \frac{\tilde{w}(t) - \bar{w}(t)}{l},$$

which allow us to present the boundary conditions in a homogeneous form:

$$u(0,t) = 0, \quad u(l,t) = 0.$$

In this case, the equation itself becomes inhomogeneous

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} + 2a \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = c^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} - H(t) - xR(t).$$

It is solved under new initial conditions

$$u(x,0) = w^{(0)}(x) - C_0(0) - C_1(0)x,$$

$$\frac{\partial u(x,0)}{\partial t} = w^{(t)}(x) - C'_0(0) - C'_1(0)x$$

and under already known homogeneous boundary conditions.

Here and below we use the notation

$$H(t) = C''_0(t) + 2aC'_0(t), \quad R(t) = C''_1(t) + 2aC'_1(t).$$

Let's start solving the equation for the auxiliary function. The equations and boundary conditions are linear. This facilitates the process of solving the problem, and we look for a solution in the form of a sum of superposition of two solutions [16,17].

The first term $U(x,t)$ is the general solution of the homogeneous equation

$$\frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial t^2} + 2a \frac{\partial U}{\partial t} = c^2 \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x^2}$$

for given boundary $U(0,t) = 0, U(l,t) = 0$ and initial conditions

$$U(x,0) = w^{(0)}(x) - C_0(0) - C_1(0)x,$$

$$\frac{\partial U(x,0)}{\partial t} = w^{(t)}(x) - C'_0(0) - C'_1(0)x.$$

The second term $V(x,t)$ represents a particular solution of the inhomogeneous equation in accordance with the right-hand side

$$\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial t^2} + 2a \frac{\partial V}{\partial t} = c^2 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} - H(t) - xR(t),$$

which is solved for zero initial

$$V(x,0) = 0, \quad \frac{\partial V(x,0)}{\partial t} = 0.$$

and homogeneous boundary conditions

$$V(0,t) = 0, \quad V(l,t) = 0.$$

First, the homogeneous equation is solved.

Let's assume that

$$U(x,t) = X(x)Y(t),$$

and we come to the equations:

$$\frac{Y''(t) + 2aY'(t)}{c^2Y(t)} = \frac{X''(x)}{X(x)} = -\lambda^2.$$

The Sturm-Liouville problem on the coordinate x gives [16,17,18]

$$X_n(x) = \sin \lambda_n x, \quad \lambda_n = \frac{n\pi}{l}, \quad \|X_n(x)\|^2 = \frac{l}{2}.$$

Moreover, to determine the multiplier in the form of an eigenfunction of time, we have the equation

$$Y_n''(t) + 2aY_n'(t) + c^2\lambda_n^2 Y_n(t) = 0. \quad (2)$$

Substituting the expression $Y_n(t) = e^{s_n t}$ into this equation will result in the characteristic equation

$$s_n^2 + 2as_n + c^2\lambda_n^2 = 0.$$

The discriminant of this equation is

$$D_n = a^2 - c^2\lambda_n^2,$$

and the solutions to the quadratic equation will be:

$$(s_n)_{1,2} = -a \pm \sqrt{D_n}.$$

When $D_n > 0$, when two roots of the characteristic equation are real and different, the solution to the differential equation $Y_n(t)$ will be [19]:

$$\begin{aligned} Y_n(t) &= A'_n e^{-at + \sqrt{D_n}t} + B'_n e^{-at - \sqrt{D_n}t} = e^{-at} \left(A'_n e^{\sqrt{D_n}t} + B'_n e^{-\sqrt{D_n}t} \right) = \\ &= e^{-at} \left(\frac{A_n + B_n}{2} e^{\sqrt{D_n}t} + \frac{A_n - B_n}{2} e^{-\sqrt{D_n}t} \right) = e^{-at} \left(A_n ch\sqrt{D_n}t + B_n sh\sqrt{D_n}t \right). \end{aligned}$$

When $D_n = 0$ the solutions to the characteristic equation are the same (double root) and the solution to the differential equation $Y_n(t)$ will be [19]:

$$Y_n(t) = e^{-at} (A_n + B_n t).$$

When $D_n < 0$ solving the characteristic equation there will be conjugate complex ones: $(s_n)_{1,2} = -a \pm i\sqrt{|D_n|}$. Therefore, solving the differential equation according to $Y_n(t)$ will [20]

$$\begin{aligned} Y_n(t) &= A'_n e^{-at + i\sqrt{|D_n|}t} + B'_n e^{-at - i\sqrt{|D_n|}t} = e^{-at} \left(A'_n e^{i\sqrt{|D_n|}t} + B'_n e^{-i\sqrt{|D_n|}t} \right) = \\ &= e^{-at} \left(\frac{A_n - iB_n}{2} e^{i\sqrt{|D_n|}t} + \frac{A_n + iB_n}{2} e^{-i\sqrt{|D_n|}t} \right) = e^{-at} \left(A_n chi\sqrt{|D_n|}t - iB_n shi\sqrt{|D_n|}t \right) = \\ &= e^{-at} \left(A_n \cos\sqrt{|D_n|}t + B_n \sin\sqrt{|D_n|}t \right). \end{aligned}$$

Taking into account these possible options $D_n > 0$, $D_n = 0$ and $D_n < 0$ for $Y_n(t)$ we get the solution:

$$Y_n(t) = \begin{cases} e^{-at} (A_n ch\sqrt{D_n}t + B_n sh\sqrt{D_n}t) & \text{при } D_n > 0, \\ e^{-at} (A_n + B_n t) & \text{при } D_n = 0, \\ e^{-at} (A_n \cos\sqrt{|D_n|}t + B_n \sin\sqrt{|D_n|}t) & \text{при } D_n < 0. \end{cases}$$

Accordingly, the general solution to the homogeneous equation is

$$U(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} Y_n(t) \sin \lambda_n x.$$

We proceed to the implementation of boundary conditions for the general solution of the homogeneous equation.

From the first initial condition (at $t = 0$) it follows:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n \sin \lambda_n x = w^{(0)}(x) - C_0(0) - xC_1(0).$$

Let's multiply the sides of this equation by $\sin \lambda_n x dx$ and integrate from zero to l . As a result we get

$$A_n \|X_n(x)\|^2 = W_n - C_0(0)S_n - C_1(0)K_n,$$

Where

$$W_n = \int_0^l w^{(0)}(x) \sin \lambda_n x dx,$$

$$S_n = \int_0^l \sin \lambda_n x dx = \frac{l}{n\pi} [1 - (-1)^n],$$

$$K_n = \int_0^l x \sin \lambda_n x dx = \frac{l^2}{n\pi} (-1)^{n+1}.$$

From here we define

$$A_n = \frac{2}{l} [W_n - C_0(0)S_n - C_1(0)K_n].$$

The second initial condition is related to the derivative of the function $U(x, t)$ with respect to time at $t = 0$.

We find

$$Y'_n(t) = \begin{cases} e^{-at} \left[(-aB_n + \sqrt{D_n} A_n) sh \sqrt{D_n} t + (-aA_n + \sqrt{D_n} B_n) ch \sqrt{D_n} t \right] & \text{при } D_n > 0, \\ e^{-at} \left[-a(A_n + B_n t) + B_n \right] & \text{при } D_n = 0, \\ e^{-at} \left[(-aB_n - \sqrt{|D_n|} A_n) \sin \sqrt{D_n} t + (-aA_n + \sqrt{|D_n|} B_n) \cos \sqrt{D_n} t \right] & \text{при } D_n < 0. \end{cases}$$

Let's calculate

$$Y'_n(0) = \begin{cases} -aA_n + \sqrt{D_n} B_n & \text{при } D_n > 0, \\ -aA_n + B_n & \text{при } D_n = 0, \\ -aA_n + \sqrt{|D_n|} B_n & \text{при } D_n < 0 \end{cases} = -aA_n + \gamma_n B_n,$$

Where $\gamma_n = \begin{cases} \sqrt{D_n} & \text{при } D_n > 0, \\ 1 & \text{при } D_n = 0, \\ \sqrt{|D_n|} & \text{при } D_n < 0. \end{cases}$

Then the second initial condition takes the form:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (-aA_n + \gamma_n B_n) \sin \lambda_n x = w^{(t)}(x) - C'_0(0) - xC'_1(0).$$

Applying the orthonormality of the eigenfunctions with respect to x , for $W_n^{(t)} = \int_0^l w^{(t)}(\eta) \sin \lambda_n \eta d\eta$, leads to the equality

$$(-aA_n + \gamma_n B_n) \frac{l}{2} = W_n^{(t)} - C_0'(0)S_n - C_1'(0)K_n.$$

From here we find the values of the coefficients

$$B_n = \frac{a}{\gamma_n} A_n + \frac{2}{\gamma_n l} \left[W_n^{(t)} - C_0'(0)S_n - C_1'(0)K_n \right].$$

The values of the coefficients of the general solution of the homogeneous equation are determined. Now we move on to solving the inhomogeneous equation.

We believe, that

$$V(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} L_n(t) \sin \lambda_n x,$$

thus fulfilling the boundary conditions $V(0, t) = 0, V(l, t) = 0$.

Substituting this solution into the inhomogeneous equation leads to the equation

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[L_n''(t) + 2aL_n'(t) + c^2 \lambda_n^2 L_n(t) \right] \sin \lambda_n x = -H(t) - xR(t).$$

We use the conditions for the orthonormality of eigenfunctions $X_n(x) = \sin \lambda_n x$:

$$L_n''(t) + 2aL_n'(t) + c^2 \lambda_n^2 L_n(t) = \frac{2}{l} \left[-H(t)S_n - R(t)K_n \right]. \tag{3}$$

When $t = 0$ we have the condition $L_n(0) = 0$. From the second initial condition $\frac{\partial V(x, 0)}{\partial t} = 0$ it follows, that $L_n'(0) = 0$.

In general, cases where functions $L_n(t)$ are defined analytically are considered. This class includes cases of linear, exponential, trigonometric and some other forms of specifying boundary conditions for speed. In this case, the final solution for the auxiliary function $u(x, t)$ is determined in the form

$$u(x, t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[Y_n(t) + L_n(t) \right] \sin \lambda_n x.$$

Going back, we obtain a solution to the problem in terms of speed

$$w(x, t) = C_0(t) + xC_1(t) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[Y_n(t) + L_n(t) \right] \sin \lambda_n x.$$

We find the solution to the problem regarding pressure by integrating the original system of quasi-one-dimensional equations.

In the first step of the solution $P(x, t)$, we turn to the second equation $\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = -\rho c^2 \frac{\partial w}{\partial x}$ of the original system.

We find

$$\frac{\partial w(x, t)}{\partial x} = C_1(t) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n \left[Y_n(t) + L_n(t) \right] \cos \lambda_n x.$$

As a result of integrating the second equation of the original system, we obtain the formula for pressure:

$$P(x, t) = -\rho c^2 \left[C_1^{(0)}(t) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n [Y_n^{(0)}(t) + L_n^{(0)}(t)] \cos \lambda_n x \right] + p_t(x).$$

Here

$$\int_0^t C_1(\theta) dt = C_1^{(0)}(t) \quad \text{And} \quad \int_0^t L_n(\theta) d\theta = L_n^{(0)}(t),$$

$$Y_n^{(0)}(t) = \int_0^t Y_n(\theta) d\theta = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{c^2 \lambda_n^2} \left[(-A_n a - B_n \sqrt{D_n}) (e^{-at} \operatorname{ch} \sqrt{D_n} t - 1) + \right. \\ \left. + (-A_n \sqrt{D_n} - B_n a) e^{-at} \operatorname{sh} \sqrt{D_n} t \right] & \text{при } D_n > 0, \\ A_n \frac{1 - e^{-at}}{a} + B_n \left(-\frac{te^{-at}}{a} + \frac{1 - e^{-at}}{a^2} \right) & \text{при } D_n = 0, \\ \frac{1}{c^2 \lambda_n^2} \left[(-A_n a - B_n \sqrt{|D_n|}) (e^{-at} \cos \sqrt{|D_n|} t - 1) + \right. \\ \left. + (A_n \sqrt{|D_n|} - B_n a) e^{-at} \sin \sqrt{|D_n|} t \right] & \text{при } D_n < 0. \end{cases}$$

When using a solution for the case $a \rightarrow 0$ (when the friction force is negligible), the expression $Y_n^{(0)}(t)$ must take into account the values of the limits

$$e^{-at} \rightarrow 1, \quad \frac{1 - e^{-at}}{a} \rightarrow t, \quad -\frac{te^{-at}}{a} + \frac{1 - e^{-at}}{a^2} \rightarrow t^2$$

and accept

$$\lim_{a \rightarrow 0} \left[A_n \frac{1 - e^{-at}}{a} + B_n \left(-\frac{te^{-at}}{a} + \frac{1 - e^{-at}}{a^2} \right) \right] = A_n t + B_n t^2.$$

It is necessary to determine the value $p_t(x)$ of constant integration over time. To determine it, let us turn to the first equation $-\frac{\partial P}{\partial x} = \rho \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + 2aw \right)$ of the original system.

Let's calculate

$$\frac{\partial P(x, t)}{\partial x} = \rho c^2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n^2 [Y_n^{(0)}(t) + L_n^{(0)}(t)] \sin \lambda_n x + p_t'(x)$$

And

$$\frac{\partial w(x, t)}{\partial t} = C_0'(t) + x C_1'(t) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [Y_n'(t) + L_n'(t)] \sin \lambda_n x.$$

We insert these expressions and the expression for speed $w(x, t)$ into the first equation of the original system:

$$-\rho c^2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n^2 [Y_n^{(0)}(t) + L_n^{(0)}(t)] \sin \lambda_n x - p_t'(x) =$$

$$= \rho \left[C_0'(t) + xC_1'(t) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [Y_n'(t) + L_n'(t)] \sin \lambda_n x \right] + 2a\rho \left[C_0(t) + xC_1(t) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [Y_n(t) + L_n(t)] \sin \lambda_n x \right].$$

From here we find

$$p_t'(x) = -\rho [C_0'(t) + 2aC_0(t)] - \rho [C_1'(t) + 2aC_1(t)]x - \rho \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [Y_n'(t) + 2aY_n(t) + c^2 \lambda_n^2 Y_n^{(0)}(t)] \sin \lambda_n x - \rho \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [L_n'(t) + 2aL_n(t) + c^2 \lambda_n^2 L_n^{(0)}(t)] \sin \lambda_n x.$$

Let's convert the first sum

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [Y_n'(t) + 2aY_n(t) + c^2 \lambda_n^2 Y_n^{(0)}(t)] \sin \lambda_n x = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^t [Y_n''(\theta) + 2aY_n'(\theta) + c^2 \lambda_n^2 Y_n(\theta)] d\theta \sin \lambda_n x = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} c_n \sin \lambda_n x d\theta = E(x).$$

Here it was taken into account that $\int_0^t [Y_n''(\theta) + 2aY_n'(\theta) + c^2 \lambda_n^2 Y_n(\theta)] d\theta = c_n = const$

represents the coefficients of expansion of the eigenfunctions of a certain function $E(x)$.

We will do the same with the second sum (sm (3)):

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [L_n'(t) + 2aL_n(t) + c^2 \lambda_n^2 L_n^{(0)}(t)] \sin \lambda_n x = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^t [L_n''(\theta) + 2aL_n'(\theta) + c^2 \lambda_n^2 L_n(\theta)] d\theta \sin \lambda_n x = \int_0^t \frac{2}{l} [-H(\theta)S_n - R(\theta)K_n] d\theta = \frac{2}{l} [-H^{(0)}(t)S_n - R^{(0)}K_n].$$

Here $H^{(0)}(t) = \int_0^t H(\theta) d\theta$, $R^{(0)}(t) = \int_0^t R(\theta) d\theta$.

When substituting the resulting sum values, we have

$$p_t'(x) = -\rho [C_0'(t) + 2aC_0(t)] - \rho [C_1'(t) + 2aC_1(t)]x - \rho E(x) + \rho \frac{2}{l} [H^{(0)}(t)S_n + R^{(0)}K_n] = -\rho \left[C_0'(t) + 2aC_0(t) - \frac{2}{l} (H^{(0)}(t)S_n + R^{(0)}(t)K_n) \right] - \rho [C_1'(t) + 2aC_1(t)]x + \rho E(x).$$

Now we integrate by x :

$$p_t(x) = -\rho \left\{ C_0'(t) + 2aC_0(t) - \frac{2}{l} [H^{(0)}(t)S_n + R^{(0)}(t)K_n] \right\} x - \rho [C_1'(t) + 2aC_1(t)] \frac{x^2}{2} + \rho \int_0^x E(\eta) d\eta.$$

Let's insert the resulting expression into the formula for pressure:

$$P(x,t) = \rho c^2 C_n^{(0)}(t) - \rho \left\{ C_0'(t) + 2aC_0(t) - \frac{2}{l} [H^{(0)}(t)S_n + R^{(0)}(t)K_n] \right\} x - \rho [C_1'(t) + 2aC_1(t)] \frac{x^2}{2} + \rho c^2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n [Y_n^{(0)}(t) + L_n^{(0)}(t)] \cos(\lambda_n x + \varphi_n) + \rho \int_0^x E(\eta) d\eta.$$

The value of the last integral is determined according to the initial pressure distribution along the length of the section, which is presented above.

At $t = 0$ the terms marked with superscripts (0) and capital letters become zero. In this regard, to determine the value of the integral we obtain the equality:

$$p_{00} - \rho \int_0^x [w^{(t)}(\eta) + 2aw^{(0)}(\eta)] d\eta = -\rho [C_0'(t) + 2aC_0(t)] x - \rho [C_1'(t) + 2aC_1(t)] \frac{x^2}{2} + \rho \int_0^x E(\eta) d\eta.$$

From here we find the value of the integral and insert it into the formula for pressure:

$$P(x,t) = p_{00} - \rho \int_0^x [w^{(t)}(\eta) + 2aw^{(0)}(\eta)] d\eta - \rho c^2 \left\{ C_1^{(0)}(t) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_n [Y_n^{(0)}(t) + L_n^{(0)}(t)] \cos \lambda_n x \right\}.$$

Here $C_1^{(0)}(t) = \frac{1}{l} \int_0^l [\bar{w}(\theta) - \tilde{w}(\theta)] d\theta.$

The physical meaning of the terms is obvious: the first term is the input pressure at the beginning of the process; the second term is the pressure drop in the initial distribution; term $c C_1^{(0)}(t)$ – change in the average pressure for a section depending on the difference between the input and output speeds; the amount reflects changes in the process of transition to another operating mode. For large values, the term $c C_1^{(0)}(t)$ can increase or decrease to infinity when $\bar{w} \neq \tilde{w}$. In this case, the time for calculating an adequate solution is limited. And after $\bar{w} = \tilde{w}$ a certain time the process is established.

Thus, the functions for boundary velocities $\bar{w}(t), \tilde{w}(t)$ are twice differentiable and integrable functions, and the functions for $w^{(0)}(x)$ and $w^{(t)}(x)$ are integrable.

We demonstrated the formal process of solving the problem. In the process of solving a problem regarding $w(x,t)$ and $P(x,t)$ individual derivatives and integrals were considered already

known. But in the calculations we limit ourselves to only considering problems of transient processes. For each case we will give specific values of derivatives and integrals.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We have compiled a program for calculating speed and pressure in transient processes in a horizontal section of a pipeline, when the initial and boundary conditions are expressed by constant values. The following values were used in the calculations: length of the section, $l = 1200 \text{ m}$, diameter of the section 0.2 m , resistance coefficient of $\lambda = 0.018$, the propagation speed of small disturbances $c = 1200 \text{ m/c}$, of the input pressure, $p_{00} = 7.0 \text{ MPa}$, speed scale $w_* = 5 \text{ m/c}$ and step along the length. $l/50$. A series of calculations were carried out with and without taking into account the friction force and in steps in time $l/(100c)$ and $l/(10c)$.

Each series included transition options: from lower speed to higher speed, from higher speed to lower speed, from initial speed to different boundary speeds. At the same values of the boundary velocities, the mass of the liquid in the elementary section remains constant; at a higher value of the input speed than the output speed, the mass of the liquid in the section increases in time linearly, and at a lower value of the input speed, vice versa.

In the first version we took $w_{00} = w^{(1)} = 0 \text{ m/c}$, $w^{(0)} = 5 \text{ m/c}$. This corresponds to the injection of water with increasing pressure in the area.

The conditional period of the process is the Velocity $T = 2l/c$. graphs had a two- and three-link structure. In the first half of the first conditional period, the velocity graphs along the length had a constant lower envelope and a newly formed upper envelope.

In the second half of the first period, the upper envelope remained as in the first half-period, and a decreasing lower envelope was formed (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Speed graphs along the length of the section at the 50th, 55th and 100th time steps at.

$$\tau = l/(100c) \quad l = 1200 \text{ m}, \quad D = 0.2 \text{ m}, \quad \lambda = 0.018, \quad w_* = 5 \text{ m/c}, \quad c = 1200 \text{ m/c},$$

$$w_{00} = w^{(1)} = 0 \text{ m/c}, \quad w^{(0)} = 5 \text{ m/c}, \quad p_{00} = 7.00 \text{ MPa}$$

In Fig. Figure 2 shows graphs of changes in flow velocity over time in various sections of the section. The numbers of time steps are located along the abscissa, at $\tau = l / (100c)$, t.e. each 100 steps represents the conditional period of the process $T = 2l / c$.

The upper curve was obtained for the section. $x = 24\text{ m}$. In general, it gradually decreases. Local minima, reached in times that are multiples of the conventional period, gradually increase.

Fig. 2. Graphs of flow velocity in various sections of the section. Data see fig. 1

The lower curve corresponds to the distance 1176 m , i.e. this point close to the end of the section. The curve gradually increases. And its local maxima correspond to points $(n + 0.5)T$. The left slopes of local maxima correspond to compaction waves, and the right slopes correspond to rarefaction waves. In intermediate curves this pattern remains valid. But for them, upper steps are formed, which are preserved over time from reaching the forward and backward waves.

In Fig. Figure 3 shows the calculation results with time steps $l / (10c)$ related to the ends and middle of the section. Here, the exponential decrease in the amplitude of velocity disturbances is more clearly expressed : a one-sided decrease in the amplitudes at the boundary nodes, and a two-sided decrease in the amplitudes at the middle nodes of the calculation.

Fig.3. Graphs of flow velocity in various sections of the section with a time step $l/(10c)$.

In Fig. Figure 4 shows pressure graphs along the length of the section, which correspond to Fig. 2 for speeds. Here, at each step, the graphs are rearranged due to an increase in the mass of liquid in the area. The same factor manifests itself in pressure versus time graphs for different sections of the section (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4. Pressure curves in the second conventional half-cycle. Data see fig. 1

In all calculation options taking into account the friction force, when the input and output speeds have the same values, the conditional period of disturbances was $T = l / c$.

Fig. 5. Pressure curves for various pipeline sections. Data see fig. 1

In Fig. 6 shows length graphs for such a case (option III) $w_{00} = 0 \text{ m/c}$, $w^{(0)} = w^{(1)} = 5 \text{ m/c}$.

Fig. 6. Velocity graphs along the length of the section, obtained in the first ten time steps at $\tau = l/(5c)$. $l = 1200 \text{ m}$, $D = 0.2 \text{ m}$, $\lambda = 0.018$, $w_* = 5 \text{ m/c}$, $c = 1200 \text{ m/c}$, $w_{00} = 0 \text{ m/c}$, $w^{(0)} = w^{(1)} = 5 \text{ m/c}$, $p_{00} = 7.00 \text{ MPa}$

In Fig. Figure 7 shows temporary changes in flow velocity in four sections of the pipeline in the first four conditional periods. And the complete picture in time is similar to the average curve from Fig. 3.

Fig. 7. Graphs of flow velocity in various sections of the section. Time $l/(100c)$.

Since the process corresponds to the start-up of a section, a certain (linear) pressure drop along the length of the section is expected. Such a transition is shown in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Change in pressure over time in different sections of the pipeline. Time $l/(10c)$.

In Fig. Figure 9 shows pressure graphs for the first conditional period. The graph with a prime corresponds to the initial condition of the problem with the input value $7.0 MPa$. The process of pressure transition in sections is shown in Fig. 10. As can be seen from these figures, the range of pressure changes narrows because the flow rate has decreased. It is interesting that after the first conditional period, the pressure value in the middle of the section remains constant.

Fig. 9. Curves of pressure versus distance at different time steps n . $w_{00} = 5 \text{ m/c}$, $w^{(0)} = w^{(1)} = 4 \text{ m/c}$. For other data, see Fig. 1

Fig. 10. Pressure dynamics in different sections of the pipeline at a large time step $l/(10c)$,

And cash payments are made for options $w^{(0)} = w^{(1)} = 5M/c$, $w^{(1)} = 6M/c$ (IV), $w^{(1)} = 4M/c$ (V), $w^{(0)} = w^{(1)} = 0M/c$ (VI). The conditional periods of options IV and V were the same $T = 2l/c$, as for option VI - $T = l/c$. Option IV showed a widespread decrease in pressure, and option V showed an increase. In option VI, a transition to uniform distributions of velocity and pressure along the length of the section was observed.

In a series of calculations at $a = 0$ ($\lambda = 0$) The results were formed under the influence of the trigonometric description of the mode amplitudes. ($D_n < 0$). As in the series for $a \neq 0$, two-, three- and five-bar curves of velocity and pressure were formed along the length of the section. The term “conditional period” applied only to pressure graphs at $w^{(0)} \neq w^{(1)}$. In each of the periods of this case, identical time graphs were obtained, and pressure surges occurred at the end of the conditional period. In other cases, only periodic solutions were obtained, because damping of disturbances does not occur due to the absence of friction force

4 CONCLUSIONS

A mathematical model of the dynamic state of an elementary relief section of a pipeline is proposed in the framework of quasi-one-dimensional equations for the transfer of momentum and fluid mass. It has been proven that the use of total pressure makes it possible to present the equations in the form of ordinary pipeline transport equations in a horizontal route.

To solve the problem, when at the ends of the section the laws of change in flow speed over time are specified, a separate equation for speed, telegraph type, was compiled, which was solved by the Fourier method. The eigenfunctions of the auxiliary problem with homogeneous boundary conditions are a sinusoidal function $X_n(x) = \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x$ and three types of amplitudes of damped disturbances:

$$Y_n(t) = \begin{cases} e^{-at} (A_n ch\sqrt{D_n}t + B_n sh\sqrt{D_n}t) & \text{при } D_n > 0, \\ e^{-at} (A_n + B_n t) & \text{при } D_n = 0, \\ e^{-at} (A_n \cos\sqrt{|D_n|}t + B_n \sin\sqrt{|D_n|}t) & \text{при } D_n < 0. \end{cases}$$

They showed that high-frequency components of disturbances are damped by an exponential law (first row), while low-frequency disturbances (third row) can take longer to penetrate. In the quasi-resonant frequency (second line), the amplitude of the disturbances has a linearly increasing factor, but the presence of an exponential factor leads to the damping of the resonant disturbances (quasi-resonant case).

Using the found velocity value and the original equations, a solution to the problem was obtained for the total pressure, which in the case of a horizontal pipeline passes to normal pressure. In the case of a positive difference between the input and output velocities, a monotonic increase in pressure in the section is expected, and in the case of a negative difference, a monotonic decrease is expected. The rate of change in the average pressure in an elementary section is proportional to the magnitude of the difference between the input speed $\bar{w} - \tilde{w}$. In this regard, $\bar{w} - \tilde{w} \neq 0$ solving the problem makes sense only for short periods of time.

It has been proven that when $a \rightarrow 0$ (ignoring the friction force) an unquenched oscillatory process with a moving boundary of the speed jump is formed.

The results of the work were obtained for a developed turbulent flow regime ($\lambda = const$) and a circular cross-section of the pipeline. To apply the results when calculating a pipeline with a different cross-sectional shape, instead of the diameter, D you can use twice the equivalent radius of the pipeline [21].

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